

APPROACH TO ESP COURSE DESIGN.

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Abstract: The following thesis explores the role of Problem -Based Learning (PBL) and case study approaches in designing English for Specific Purpose (ESP) course that is adapted for airport security officers.

Key words: airport security, problem-based learning, case study, approach, English for Specific Purpose, project, design, course.

For the purpose of creating ESP course for airport security officers, Woodrow (2018) suggested using problem-based learning and case study approaches. These approaches are an excellent approaches for my ESP project as they meet with the unique requirements and work environments of airport security officers.

PBL exposes students to real-world problems for which there is no right answer, reflecting the dynamic and unexpected nature of airport security operations. Security officers frequently come across circumstances that call for rapid thinking and problem-solving. According to Woodrow (2018), PBL fosters the development of critical thinking, flexibility, and other vital skills among students. These abilities are necessary for officers to deal with a variety of situations, including managing challenging passengers and carrying out security tasks while interacting with passengers and coworkers in an efficient manner.

The case study method is also used in the ESP setting for airport security officers in addition to PBL. Case studies offer in-depth examinations of specific incidents or circumstances, providing students with an accurate understanding of real-world contexts. Through the analysis of appropriate case studies, airport security officers can gain insights from previous experiences, both favorable and unfavorable. According to Woodrow (2018), case studies help students develop their analytical and decision-making abilities by allowing them to provide solutions based on thorough analysis and causes.

There is a lot of communication involved in case studies and PBL, whether it is through written reports, group discussions, or presentations. For airport security officers effective communication with both passengers and coworkers is essential. According to Woodrow (2018), these methods encourage students to communicate their ideas clearly and succinctly, which improves their English language skills and helps them acquire specialized vocabulary and workplace-relevant contexts.

PBL involves students actively and is a student-centered process. Learners become more engaged and motivated when they believe that the challenges they solve are important and directly related to their careers. According to Woodrow (2018), PBL raises intrinsic motivation by giving students' education a greater sense of purpose and connection to their career objectives.

Case studies draw students in by displaying thought-provoking, frequently difficult, and analytically demanding circumstances. The target group, airport security officers, are more likely to be motivated and interested when they perceive the application of what they have learned to actual circumstances. They can gain a better knowledge of their duties and responsibilities by going through such situations.

Case studies and PBL both contribute to the development of critical soft skills including leadership, time management, and teamwork. Officers in charge of airport security frequently operate in groups and must cooperate well under pressure. According to Woodrow (2018), PBL fosters teamwork since it requires students to collaborate in order to solve challenges. In the same way, case studies develop leadership and group work by requiring collaboration, communication, and group decision-making.

Incorporating PBL and case study approaches in my ESP course for airport security officers suggests several profits, such as developing critical thinking, communication skills and enhancing motivation and engagement. These approaches match with real-world requirement of airport security providing that learning practice is applicable and meaningful process. Woodrow (2018) suggested effective basis for these methods emphasizing how well they prepare professionals for challenging and significant work environment.

Adabiyotlar, References, Литературы:

1. Flowerdew, J.(2013). Needs analysis and curriculum development in ESP.
2. Lockwood, J. (2012). Developing ESP for call centers.
3. O’Sullivan, B. (2012) Assessment Issues for in Language for Specific Purpose.
4. Otto. P. (2021). Choosing specialized vocabulary to teach with data-driven learning: An example from civil engineering.
5. Serafini, E. J., Lake, J. B., & Long, M. H. (2015). Needs analysis for specialized learner populations: Essential methodological considerations.
6. Viana, V., Bocorny, A., & Sarmentoa, S. (2019). Teaching English for specific purposes. TESOL Press.
7. Woodrow, L. (2018) Introducing course design in English for specific purpose.